

AEON

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1. PROGRAM NOTES

The symbolic abstraction of origin, motion of circle, and the reflection of evolution can be implemented in numerous forms and timespans and can inspire provocative insights into everyday life. Four custom-made controllers – Yuan are used for the performance. Each controller can be performed individually or together with the other three, creating an immersive musical experience.

Fig. 1. performance photo.

2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The Yuan controller represents an inventive analogical synthesis, drawing parallel connections between fundamental concepts of time, geometric shapes, circular motion, and life cycles. Utilizing multiple tambourine drum frames, this controller offers the potential to interconnect varying numbers and sizes of controllers, incorporating functionalities such as light, motion, direction, and touch interaction. Through this, a complex network of performative actions can be orchestrated.

3. PERFORMANCE NOTES

YUAN is a data-driven instrument controller. There are three different sizes of YUAN, in *AEON*, two medium, and two large YUAN will be used for the

performer. The hardware of YUAN is made from tambourine bamboo frame, conductive steel thread, Adafruit Circuit Playground microcontroller.

Capacitive touch

Performer can engage the capacitive touch sensors 1, 2, 3, and 4 by plucking the steel strings, or the nails attached.

Motion detective

Performer can pick up, rotate sideways, rotate forward and backward to produce orientation values of YUAN.

4. MEDIA LINK

- Video: <https://vimeo.com/896608380>